

Oxidation behavior of the SiC fiber reinforced SiO₂- mullite composites

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SUMMARY:

Effect of glass coating on the anti-oxidation ability for CVD carbon interphase in the newly developed unidirectional sintered SiC_f/ SiO₂- mullite composites was investigated.

A magnesium alumino-silicate (MAS) glass with approximately 30 μm-thick was coated on the composite. Oxidation behavior at the temperature of 1573 K in the air and the effect of exposure time on the three-point flexural strength of the composites with or without glass-coating were investigated. As a result, reduction of the glassy phase are found which were caused by precipitation of crystalized phases in the MAS glass layer. This was confirmed by SEM and XRD. The ultimate strength of the non glass-coated specimen decreased to 1/3 of initial strength within 3.6 ksec. On the other hand, as to the glass-coated specimen, initial strength was kept up to 36 ksec after exposure. After 360 ksec exposure, the strength decreased to 1/2 of the initial strength, and it was found that the pyrograph CVD carbon layer was partially oxidized from the longitudinal ends. This means that SiO₂- mullite oxide matrix is protective for the oxidization of the carbon layer because no oxidization was found in the transverse direction of the composite. However, after degradation of MAS glass coating, once the oxidization began from either end of the specimen, the air gap between the fiber and matrix accerarated the oxidization along to the fiber direction. Self crack repairbility by the MAS glass coating is also examined by conducting a notch in the transverse direction of the composites. Though the carbon layer in the non-coated composite disappeared after 3.6 ks exposure, as to the coated composites, the oxidized area around the notch was limited within 2~3 mm in the direction of the fiber after 36 ksec exposure.

KEYWORDS: CMC, glass coating, oxidation, flexural strength, self-repairbility

INTRODUCTION

Silicon carbide (SiC) fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites have been developed as a candidate for toughened thermo-structural materials [1]. Damage tolerant characteristics of ceramic matrix composite (CMC) arise because of stress redistribution mechanism, involving matrix cracking and stochastic fiber failure, accompanied by debonding and sliding interface [2-4]. All of the damage tolerant CMCs have relied on a thin weak interphase between the fiber and the matrix. The interphase used in most commercial products consists of either carbon or boron nitride [5].

The newly developed composite used in this study consists of a sintered SiC fiber with CVD carbon coating and SiO₂- mullite double phase oxide material. It is known that the SiC fiber has excellent phase stability and its mechanical properties remain up to 2173 K [6]. Furthermore, it is known that SiO₂ has the lowest oxygen permeability in any oxide material [7]. Mullite (3Al₂O₃•2SiO₂) is known as a potential ceramic material for high temperature structure applications because of its chemical and thermal stability, and excellent high-temperature creep behavior [8,9].

The carbon fiber coatings should be protected from oxidation in order to keep the stress transfer between the fiber and the matrix, because the fiber coating is sensitive to oxidation at temperature above 773 K [10]. It is reported that by oxidization of a SiC fiber, 10 ~ 20 nm-thick carbon layer are formed between SiO₂ layer and the fiber. This SiO₂ layer is effective to

protect the carbon layer. [11] In the other case, the coating of Na₂O- SiO₂ water glass on the composites is also effective to protect carbon layer in the composite [12].

In this work, about 1 μm thickness of CVD graphite was coated on the surface of the sintered SiC fiber. Then UD SiC fiber reinforced SiO₂- mullite matrix composite was fabricated by hot-pressing in the semi-solid state of oxide matrix. Then effect of magnesium aluminosilicate (MAS) glass coating on the anti-oxidation ability and three-point flexural strength was examined after exposure at 1573 K for 3.6~360 ks. In order to clarify the oxidation resistivity after cracking, a notch was conducted into the MAS glass coated composite. After exposure at 1573 K for 3.6~36 ks, oxidation behavior was observed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials

The sintered SiC fiber “Tyranno SA” tows with average diameter of 7.5 μm from Ube Industry Ltd. was used as the reinforcement. The fibers were coated with 0.8 μm-thick carbon layer by using chemical vapor deposition (Pyrograph, Toyo Tanso Co., Ltd.). The chemical composition of the oxide matrix is SiO₂- 30mol. % Al₂O₃. Influence of the Al₂O₃ content in the matrix on the mechanical properties has already investigated. This composition was determined by high temperature properties of the composites. SiO₂ powder (SO-C2, Admatechs Co., Ltd.) and Al₂O₃ powder (AKP-30, Sumitomo Chemical Co., Ltd.) were selected as starting materials for the matrix. At the hot-press temperature of 1923 K, the oxide material includes primary mullite crystals and liquid phase. This semi-solid processing is effective to obtain well densified matrix in the composites [13]. A frit material “MAS glass” (FF201, Asahi Techno Glass Co.) was selected as a starting material of the glass-coating. Chemical composition and properties of the material are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Properties of the as- received MAS- glass powder.

composition	MgO : 11 (mass %) Al ₂ O ₃ : 28 SiO ₂ : 44 ZnO : 7 B ₂ O ₃ : 10
average diameter	1.8 (μm)
glass transition temp.	993 (K)
softening temp.	1093 (K)
crystallization start temp.	1228 (K)
crystallization complete temp.	1273 (K)

Fabrication process

The slurry for matrix was prepared by dispersing the SiO₂ powder and Al₂O₃ powder into distilled water with a planetary ball-milling machine. The fiber tows were impregnated by the slurry and dried at 343 K for 86.4 ksec. The composite preform was hot-pressed at the conditions of 30 MPa for 3.6 ks at 1923 K in vacuum (10⁻² Pa) and then cooled at the rate of 5 K/ min. An unidirectionally reinforced composite was obtained with the dimensions of 20 mm (width) × 80 mm (length) × approximately 5 mm (thickness). The longitudinal direction of the specimens corresponded to the fiber axis direction. The obtained composite was cut into the flexural specimens with dimensions of 4 mm (width) × 40 mm (length) × 3 mm (thickness).

The glass powder was dispersed in distilled water by ball-milling. The specimens were immersed into the slurry and kept in decompression chamber at the pressure of 34.66 kPa for 300 sec. Then, the specimens were dried at 373 K for 86.4 ksec. Thereafter the dried specimens were heat-treated in a vacuum chamber at the conditions of 2.0 × 10⁻² Pa for 3.6 ks at 1273 K in order to form the glass-coating layer on the specimens.

For the crack self-repairability test, a notch which has dimensions of 300 μm -width and approximately 500 μm -depth and 4 mm-width was introduced at the center of the flexural specimens perpendicular to the fiber axis with a diamond wheel.

Observation of the as-coated specimen

The cross section of glass-coated specimen was observed by using an optical microscope and a scanning electron microscope (SEM). The volume fraction of the pores in the glass-coating layer/ composite interface was measured from the optical microscope image.

Oxidation test

The oxidation test was conducted in a boxy furnace (KBF333N, Koyo Lindberg Co., Ltd) at 1573 K under the conditions shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Conditions of the oxidation test.

specimen		oxidation time (ksec)
SiC _f / SiO ₂ - 30mol. %Al ₂ O ₃	glass coated	3.6, 36, 360
	non coated	3.6

(a) Three-point flexural test

Three-point flexural test was conducted on the oxidized specimens at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/ min at 298 K. The span length of lower pins was 30 mm. An universal testing machine Shimadzu Autograph AG-50G was used.

(b) Microstructure observation

After oxidation, each specimen was cut into halves in the longitudinal direction. Then thickness of the glass-coating layer was measured. The cross section of the cut specimen was observed by using SEM.

(c) X-ray diffraction (XRD)

In this experiment, SiO₂- 30mol. % Al₂O₃ balk without SiC fibers was prepared in order to exclude the influence of oxidation of SiC fiber on the diffusion process between MAS glass and the matrix. X-ray diffraction (MXP¹⁸VA, Mac Science Co., Ltd.) was performed to identify the crystalline phases in the glass-coating layer as a function of the oxidation time.

Self-repairability of crack

Self-repairability of crack was examined by using pre-notched specimens. The specimens were oxidized under the conditions shown in Table 2. The cross section of the oxidized specimens was polished and observed by optical microscope or stereoscope.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Observation of the as-coated specimen

Appearance and cross section of the as-coated specimen are shown in Fig.1. Although the coating layer is formed in vacuum atmosphere above the glass transition temperature, pores are found in the coating layer or the coating layer/ composite interface. The pores seemed to be formed by migration of pre-existed gases in the as-received MAS glass powder. The volume fraction of the pores in the interface was nearly 8 %.

Fig.1 Observation of the glass coated specimen. (a): photograph image, (b) optical microscope image, (c): SEM image

Oxidation test

(a) Three-point flexural test

The ultimate strength of the specimens versus the oxidation time is shown in Fig. 2. The strength of the oxidized non glass-coated specimen degraded to 1/3 of the initial strength within 3.6 ksec. On the contrary, that of the glass-coated specimen kept up to 36 ksec. After exposure of 360 ksec, the strength degraded to 1/2 of the initial strength.

Fig. 2 Effect of exposure time and the glass coating on the flexural-strength of the composite.

(b) Observation of the oxidized specimens

Figure 3 shows SEM images of the surface of the glass-coating layer after oxidized for 3.6 or 360 ksec. Both crystalline phases and glassy phase were observed in the coating layer after 3.6 ksec. On the other hand, after 360 ksec, glassy phase was scarcely found in the coating layer. Only crystalline phases were observed. Figure 4 shows SEM images of the cross section of the specimen near the surface after the oxidation tests. Thickness of the coating layer reduced according to the oxidation time. No carbon fiber coating was found in the non glass-coated specimen exposed for 3.6 ksec. Figure 5 shows the optical microscope images of the cross sections of the composites. In the specimens with the glass-coating exposed for 3.6 or 36 ksec, the carbon fiber coatings remained and no clear oxidation was found. In the specimens exposed for 360 ksec, a part of carbon coating was disappeared by oxidation. Adjacent to the SiC fibers without carbon layer by oxidation, the fibers with carbon layer were found. This means that the oxidation progress along to the fiber, however, as to the direction perpendicular to the fiber, the oxide matrix interrupts the transport of the oxizen. After the crystallization of MAS glass coating layer, the ability to prevent oxidation of the carbon layer degrades. Then the oxidation progress from the longitudinal ends of the specimens into the inner part of th composite. The decrease of the strength due to the oxidation time will be caused by the reduction of stress transfer between the fiber and the matrix.

Fig. 3 SEM images of surface area of the glass-coating layer on the composite exposed for (a) 3.6 ksec and (b) 360 ksec at 1573K.

Fig. 4 SEM images of the end region of the oxidized specimen in longitudinal section.

Fig. 5 Optical microscope images of the inner composite body in the oxidized specimens with glass coating.

(c) XRD

Cordierite ($2\text{MgO}\cdot 2\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\cdot 5\text{SiO}_2$), gahnite spinel (ZnAl_2O_4) and mullite phases were identified in XRD profile. It is known that cordierite and gahnite spinel phases precipitate from the MAS glass. During heat treatment of MAS glass, in this case during exposure at 1573 K, these crystalline phases grows from glass phase. The peak of mullite should come from matrix in the composite under the coating. As shown above, the precipitation of cordierite and gahnite spinel phases leads to decrease of the volume of glassy phase. Furthermore, it is known that B_2O_3 in the glass phase tend to vaporize at high temperature. This also promotes the crystallization of the glass. These factors will cause the reduction of the

volume of the coating and lead to form the pass to transport oxygen into the composite.

Fig. 6 XRD profiles of the glass-coating. (a): before oxidation test, (b): 3.6 ksec oxidized, (c): 36 ksec oxidized, (d): 360 ksec oxidized

Self-repairability of crack

The optical microscope images of the notched specimens after the oxidation tests are shown in Fig. 7. The air gap was found between the fiber and the matrix near the notch in the specimens exposed for 3.6 or 36 ksec. However, growth of the gap along to the fibers were clearly limited compared to the oxidation behavior from both ends of the non-coated composites. This means that when a crack induced perpendicular to the fibers into the composite, the oxidation of carbon layer progress along the fiber as a certain degree. Then the coated glass material spreads into the crack and prevents further oxidation from the crack. Figure 8 shows the stereoscopic images of the notched specimens after exposure for 3.6 or 36 ks. This figure also reveals that the oxidized area does not grow until 36 ks after exposure.

However, after exposure of 360 ks, almost all the carbon layer disappeared. This will be caused by the degradation of crack sealing ability of migrated MAS glass as mentioned above.

Fig. 7 Optical microscope images around the notch after the oxidation tests.

Fig. 8 Optical microscope images and schematic illustrations of the specimens with a notch after the oxidation tests.

CONCLUSIONS

Effect of magnesium alumino-silicate (MAS) glass coating on the anti-oxidation ability for carbon interphase in the sintered SiC fiber reinforced SiO₂ – mullite oxide matrix composite was investigated. The specimens are exposed in the air at 1573 K for 3.6, 36 or 360 ks. Then the oxidation behavior with or without notch and remained flexural strength of the composites

were examined. The results are as follows.

1. As to the coated composites, initial strength was kept after 36 ks exposure. However, after exposure of 360 ks, the strength decreased to 1/2 of the initial strength.
2. The oxidation protectivity by the coating degrades after exposure of 360 ks. This will be caused by the precipitation of the crystalline phases from glass phase and formation of open pass in the coating layer.
3. In the self-crack repairability test, it was found that the coated-glass migrated into the notch and covered its surface. The growth of the oxidated area was limited compared to the non-coated specimen.

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